

Contributions to the Heteroptera (Hemiptera) Fauna of Giresun Province

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ABSTRACT: In this study, 63 species belonging to 15 families of the Heteroptera suborder were identified as a result of field studies conducted in 26 localities in Bulancak District of Giresun Province in August 2025. Of these, 7 species are new records for the Black Sea Region, 8 species for the Eastern Black Sea Region, and 24 species for Giresun Province. Among these species, *Stenodema holsata*, *Stephanitis caucasica*, and *Paraparomius leptopoides* (Baerensprung, 1859) are known to be rarely recorded in Türkiye.

KEYWORDS: Heteroptera, fauna, new record, Giresun, Türkiye

INTRODUCTION

Heteroptera is the largest suborder of the Hemiptera order, with over 45,000 species worldwide and over 10,000 in the Palearctic region. It is distributed all continents, except Antarctica (Henry, 2017, Aukema, 2018). The first studies to determine the Heteroptera fauna in Türkiye The first studies to determine the Heteroptera fauna in Türkiye have increased steadily since the late 19th century (Çerçi et al., 2024). In their study, Çerçi et al. (2024) reviewed all studies conducted in Türkiye and determined

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that 1668 species had been recorded from the country so far (664 species in the European part and 1633 species in the Anatolian part), but noted that 37 of these species needed to be confirmed.

Furthermore, when researchers classified the species corotypically, they found that 399 species were Mediterranean elements (23.9%), 380 species were European elements (22.8%), 280 species were local (16.8%), 182 species were widespread (10.9%), 128 species were endemic (7.7%), 127 species were Turanian (7.5%), 89 species were Turano-Mediterranean (5.3%), 68 species were European-Mediterranean (4.1%), and 12 species were foreign (0.7%).

Additionally, when researchers considered species diversity by province, they concluded that the number of species recorded in provinces in the Eastern Anatolia, Southeastern Anatolia, and Black Sea regions was lower compared to provinces in other regions. One reason for the lower number of species recorded in these regions is likely the fact that fewer studies have been conducted there.

This study, conducted to determine the Heteroptera fauna in Bulancak District of Giresun Province in the Eastern Black Sea region, aims to contribute to the understanding of the fauna of both Giresun and the Black Sea Region.

The study area, Bulancak district is located along the Black Sea coast in an east-west direction and is one of the largest districts of Giresun. Rural settlements in the mountainous area behind the coast are mostly concentrated in valley bottoms and slopes.

Much of the district's coastal strip consists of Quaternary-aged alluvium carried by various streams, primarily the Pazarsuyu Stream, that flow into the Black Sea.

Behind the coast, there is a mountainous and rugged topography composed of Upper Cretaceous volcanic materials such as agglomerate, andesite, basalt, and tuff (Şahin et al., 2017).

The Bulancak district's climate, characterized by rainfall in every season, supports plant growth. Forests located along the coastline and in lower areas have been largely destroyed for purposes such as creating settlements and agricultural land. Hazelnut cultivation is widespread in the region.

In areas where forests have been destroyed, shrub-like plants, some of which contain Mediterranean elements, have become dominant.

Forest cover in the district extends from 300-400 meters to 2000 meters, where alpine vegetation begins. Beech forests, starting from areas near the coast and reaching up to 1700 meters, form mixed forests with spruce trees between 500-1200 meters. After 1500 meters, pure groves and spruce forests mixed with fir trees are observed (Bekdemir, 2004).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, Heteroptera specimens were collected from 26 different localities in Giresun province between August 17 and 30, 2025 (Table 1, Fig. 1).

Fieldwork was carried out using sweep nets on herbaceous plants, a beating tray from shrubs and trees, and an aspirator from the soil surface and the lower parts of plants. Péricart (1983, 1998a-c), Poisson (1957), Wagner (1970, 1971) and Moulet (1995) were used for the species identification.

Table 1. Localities where fieldwork was conducted in Bulancak District, Giresun Province in August 2025, including coordinates, altitude and data collection dates.

Loc. No	Locality name	Coordinate	Altitude	Date
1	Bulancak-Yaslıbahçe Village (Tatarlı Küme Evler)	40.85856, 38.21305	490m	18.08.2025
2	Bulancak-Yaslıbahçe Village (graveyard)	40.86115, 38.21750	433m	18.08.2025
3	Bulancak-Uçarlı district	40.91800, 38.24500	60m	19.08.2025
4	Bulancak-Talıpli Village	40.93367, 38.26819	218m	19.08.2025
5	Bulancak-Dikmendağı Hill	40.92200, 38.26835	475m	19.08.2025
6	Bulancak-Kuzköy	40.82400, 38.20780	455m	19.08.2025
7	Bulancak-Tepecik Village	40.85000, 38.21080	624m	20.08.2025
8	Bulancak-Kuşluhan Village	40.89742, 38.24180	378m	20.08.2025
9	Bulancak-Yaslıbahçe (stream)	40.85505, 38.22015	303m	20.08.2025
10	Bulancak-Saraçlı District	40.91589, 38.20454	53m	21.08.2025
11	Bulancak-Yeşilhisar Village	40.86738, 38.15652	100m	21.08.2025
12	Bulancak-Ezeltere Village	40.70543, 38.23748	1581m	22.08.2025
13	Bulancak-Ericealan Plateau (next to the forest)	40.66881, 38.21859	1976m	23.08.2025
14	Ericealan Plateau Gamar Obası	40.66881, 38.21859	1976 m	23.08.2025
15	Bulancak-Karapınar Plateau	40.67866, 38.18901	1893m	23.08.2025
16	Bulancak-Ericealan Plateau (forest)	40.67008, 38.22273	1910m	23.08.2025
17	Bulancak-Alibeyköy	40.77456, 38.13263	378m	26.08.2025
18	Bulancak-Hacet Village	40.84198, 38.20315	709m	27.08.2025
19	Bulancak-Erdoğan Village (Bedir Hill)	40.88560, 38.20245	528m	27.08.2025
20	Bulancak-Yalıköy	40.93085, 38.29833	83m	28.08.2025

Table 1 (continued). Localities where fieldwork was conducted in Bulancak District, Giresun Province in August 2025, including coordinates, altitude and data collection dates.

21	Dereli-Taşlıca Village	40.77258, 38.44145	204m	28.08.2025
22	Keşap-Karabedir District	40.89680, 38.49170	292m	28.08.2025
23	Center-Kayadibi District	40.88929, 38.38847	376m	28.08.2025
24	Center-Eriklimanı Village	40.90052, 38.28009	455m	28.08.2025
25	Bulancak-Büyükada Village	40.83272, 38.17522	241m	29.08.2025
26	Bulancak-Büyükada Village (Sarımsa)	40.82122, 38.18235	608m	29.08.2025

Figure 1. Localities where research was conducted in Giresun Province (Google earth)

RESULTS

Cimicomorpha: Cimicoidea: Anthocoridae: Anthocorinae: Anthocorini

***Anthocoris nemorum* (Linnaeus, 1761)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak-Ezeltete Village (1581 m): 22.08.2025, 1♂, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Antalya, Artvin, Bolu, Erzurum, Trabzon (Önder et al., 2006; Yıldırım et al., 2013).

First record for Giresun Province.

Cimicomorpha: Cimicoidea: Anthocoridae: Anthocorinae: Oriini

***Orius minutus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak-Kuşluhan Village (378 m): 20.08.2025, 4♀♀; Erdoğan Village-Bedir Hill (528 m): 27.08.2025, 1♀; Center-Kayadibi District (376 m): 28.08.2025, 3♀♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Adıyaman, Afyonkarahisar, Ağrı, Aksaray, Amasya,

Ankara, Antalya, Ardahan, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Batman, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bingöl, Bitlis, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Hakkâri, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Kırklareli, Kırşehir, Kilis, Kocaeli, Konya, Kütahya, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Muş, Nevşehir, Niğde, Ordu, Osmaniye, Rize, Sakarya, Samsun, Siirt, Sinop, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Şırnak, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Trabzon, Tunceli, Uşak, Van, Yalova, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Yazıcı et al., 2025)

***Orius vicinus* (Ribaut, 1923)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Ezeltere Village (1581 m): 22.08.2025, 2♀♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Ankara, Antalya, Karaman, Kayseri, Konya, Mardin, Niğde, Nevşehir (Çerçi & Koçak, 2023) **First record for the Black Sea Region.**

Cimicomorpha: Miroidea: Miridae: Bryocorinae: Dicyphini

***Dicyphus albonasutus* Wagner, 1951**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak-Talıpli Village (218 m): 19.08.2025, 1♀; Hacet Village (709 m): 27.08.2025, 1♀; Sarımusa (608 m): 29.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Ankara, Antalya, Çanakkale, Diyarbakır, Hatay, İzmir (Önder & Adıgüzel, 1979; Önder et al, 2006; Kostantinov et al., 2021) **First record for the Black Sea Region.**

Cimicomorpha: Miroidea: Miridae: Mirinae: Mirini

***Adelphocoris lineolatus* (Goeze, 1778)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak-Burunucu Village, Dikmen Hill (475 m): 19.08.2025, 2♀♀; Yeşilhisar Village (100 m): 21.08.2025, 6♂♂; Alibeyköy (378 m): 26.08.2025, 1♂ 6♀♀; Büyükada Village (241 m): 29.08.2025, 1♂ 2♀♀; Dereli-Taşlıca Village (204 m): 28.08.2025, 1♂ 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Adıyaman, Afyonkarahisar, Ağrı, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bingöl, Bitlis, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa; Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hakkâri, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İçel, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Kırklareli, Kırşehir, Kilis, Kocaeli, Konya, Kütahya, Malatya, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Muş, Nevşehir, Niğde, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Samsun, Sinop, Şanlıurfa, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Trabzon, Tunceli, Van, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Tepecik & Dursun, 2023; Yazıcı & Bal, 2025) **First record for Giresun Province.**

***Adelphocoris seticornis* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak-Yaslıbahçe Village (490 m): 18.08.2025, 2♂♂ 6♀♀; Hacet Village (709 m): 27.08.2025, 1♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adapazarı, Artvin, Bartın, Bilecik, Düzce, Edirne, Erzurum, Kars, Samsun, Sinop, Zonguldak (Yazıcı, 2015). **First record for Giresun Province.**

***Liocoris tripustulatus* (Fabricius, 1781)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Kuzköy (455 m): 19.08.2025, 5♀♀; Alibeyköy (378 m): 26.08.2025, 1♀; Erdoğan Village Bedir Hill (528 m): 27.08.2025, 1♂; Yalıköy

(83 m): 28.08.2025, 1♀; Center- Eriklimanı Village (455 m): 28.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Aksaray, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bitlis, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elâzığ, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hakkâri, Hatay, Iğdır, İçel, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Konya, Kütahya, Manisa, Mardin, Nevşehir, Niğde, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Trabzon, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Tepecik & Dursun, 2023; Yazıcı & Bal, 2025) **First record for Giresun Province.**

***Lygus rugulipennis* Poppius, 1911**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Ericealan Plateau, next to the forest (1920 m): 22.08.2025, 1♀; Ericealan Plateau Gamar Obası (1976 m): 23.08.2025, 2♂♂ 19♀♀; Ericealan Plateau forest (1910 m): 23.08.2025, 1♂; Sarımusa (608 m): 29.08.2025, 1♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Adıyaman, Afyonkarahisar, Ağrı, Aksaray, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Bartın, Bilecik, Bitlis, Bingöl, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Düzce, Gaziantep, Giresun, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Hakkâri, İstanbul, İzmir, Karabük, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kırıkkale, Kırşehir, Konya, Kayseri, Kırklareli, Kocaeli, Kütahya, Malatya, Muş, Nevşehir, Niğde, Sakarya, Samsun, Sinop, Şanlıurfa, Tekirdağ, Tunceli, Uşak, Van, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Yazıcı, 2015; Tepecik & Dursun, 2023).

***Lygus pratensis* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yeşilhisar Village (100 m): 21.08.2025, 1♀;

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Adıyaman, Afyonkarahisar, Ağrı, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bilecik, Bingöl, Bitlis, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hatay, Hakkâri, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Kırklareli, Kırşehir, Kilis, Kocaeli, Konya, Kütahya, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Muş, Nevşehir, Niğde, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Samsun, Siirt, Sinop, Şanlıurfa, Trabzon, Tunceli, Uşak, Van, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Yazıcı, 2015; Kaçar & Dursun, 2022; Tepecik & Dursun, 2023). **First record for Giresun Province.**

***Orthops basalis* (A. Costa, 1853)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yashıbahçe Village, graveyard (433 m): 19.08.2025, 1♀; Kuzköy (455 m): 19.08.2025, 1♀; Yeşilhisar Village (100 m): 21.08.2025, 1♂; Alibeyköy (378 m): 26.08.2025, 1♀; Büyükkada Village Sarımusa (608 m): 29.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Ankara, Amasya, Artvin, Bayburt, Burdur, Çankırı, Erzurum, Iğdır, Kars, Ordu, Samsun (Tepecik & Dursun, 2023; Yazıcı & Bal, 2025). **First record for Giresun Province.**

***Orthops kalmii* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Kuşluhan Village (378 m): 20.08.2025, 1♀; Yeşilhisar Village (100 m): 21.08.2025, 1♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin,

Aydın, Bilecik, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hatay, İçel, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kocaeli, Mardin, Nevşehir, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Sinop, Tekirdağ, Trabzon, Uşak, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Tepecik & Dursun, 2023; Yazıcı & Bal, 2025)
First record for Giresun Province.

***Orthops montanus* (Schilling, 1837)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yashıbahçe Village, graveyard (433 m): 19.08.2025, 1♀; Kuzköy (455 m): 19.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Antalya, Erzurum, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kütahya (Yazıcı, 2015). **First record for the Black Sea Region.**

***Stenotus binotatus* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Ericealan Plateau Gamar Obası (1976 m): 23.08.2025, 7♀♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Antalya, Bolu, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Edirne, Erzurum, Hatay, Iğdır, Kars, Kastamonu, Mersin, Tekirdağ (Yazıcı & Bal, 2025) **First record for the Eastern Black Sea Region.**

Cimicomorpha: Miroidea: Miridae: Mirinae: Stenodemini

***Stenodema calcarata* (Fallén, 1807)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Burunucu Village Dikmen Hill (475 m): 19.08.2025, 1♀; Saraçlı District (53 m): 21.08.2025, 1♂, 2♀♀; Ericealan Plateau Gamar Obası (1976 m): 23.08.2025, 1♀; Center- Eriklimanı Village (455 m): 28.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bitlis, Burdur, Bursa, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, İçel, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kırklareli, Kilis, Konya, Kütahya, Muğla, Niğde, Rize, Sakarya, Samsun, Sinop, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Trabzon, Uşak, Yozgat (Tepecik & Dursun, 2023; Yazıcı & Bal, 2025). **First record for Giresun Province.**

***Stenodema holsata* (Fabricius, 1787)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Ezeltere Village (1581 m): 22.08.2025, 1♀; Ericealan Plateau Gamar Obası (1976 m): 23.08.2025, 17♀♀; Karapınar Plateau (1893 m): 23.08.2025, 1♀;

Distribution in Türkiye: Artvin, Kars, Kocaeli, Trabzon (Önder et al., 2006) **First record for Giresun Province.**

***Stenodema laevigata* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Sarımusa (608 m): 29.08.2025, 2♀♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Bolu, Bursa, Çankırı, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Erzurum, Giresun, Iğdır, İstanbul, İzmir, Kayseri, Nevşehir, Ordu, Trabzon,

Zonguldak (Yazıcı & Bal, 2025).

Cimicomorpha: Miroidea: Tingidae: Tinginae: Tingini

***Corythucha arcuata* (Say, 1832)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Karapınar Plateau (1893 m): 23.08.2025, 1♀; Center- Kayadibi District (376 m): 28.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Amasya, Ankara, Artvin, Bilecik, Bolu, Bursa, Çankırı, Düzce, Eskişehir, İstanbul, Kastamonu, Kırklareli, Kocaeli, Mersin, Niğde, Sakarya, Samsun, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Trabzon, Zonguldak (Dursun & Fent, 2017; Çerçi et al., 2021). **First record for Giresun Province.**

***Stephanitis caucasica* Kiritshenko, 1951**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Ericealan Plateau forest (1910 m): 23.08.2025, 1♂, 3♀♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Artvin, Iğdır, Sivas (Péricart, 1983; Dursun & Fent, 2017; Bulak Korkmaz et al., 2022). **First record for Giresun Province.**

Cimicomorpha: Naboidea: Nabidae: Nabinae

***Himacerus apterus* (Fabricius, 1798)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yalıbahçe Village (490 m): 18.08.2025, 1♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Balıkesir, Erzincan, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırklareli, Zonguldak (Yazıcı, 2022). **First record for the Eastern Black Sea Region.**

***Himacerus mirmicoides* (O. Costa, 1834)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yalıbahçe Village, graveyard (433 m): 19.08.2025, 1♂, 1♀; Alibeyköy (378 m): 26.08.2025, 1♀; Hacet Village (709 m): 27.08.2025, 1♀; Erdoğan Village Bedir Hill (528 m): 27.08.2025, 1♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Ağrı, Ankara, Artvin, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Bursa, Çankırı, Edirne, Elâzığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Kastamonu, Ordu, Tokat (Dursun, 2011; Yazıcı, 2022; Yazıcı et al., 2023).

***Nabis punctatus punctatus* A. Costa, 1847**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Saraçlı District (53 m): 21.08.2025, 1♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adıyaman, Afyonkarahisar, Amasya, Ankara, Batman, Burdur, Bursa, Çankırı, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elâzığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Giresun, Iğdır, Isparta, İzmir, Karaman, Kayseri, Kırşehir, Konya, Malatya, Mardin, Niğde, Şanlıurfa, Siirt, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Tokat, Van, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Dursun, 2011; Yazıcı, 2022)

***Nabis rugosus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yaslıbahçe Village (490 m): 18.08.2025, 1♀; Yaslıbahçe Village, graveyard (433 m): 19.08.2025, 6♂♂ 4♀♀; Kuzköy (455 m): 19.08.2025, 2♂♂ 3♀♀; Tepecik Village (624 m): 20.08.2025, 3♂♂ 5♀♀; Alibeyköy (378 m): 26.08.2025, 3♂♂ 1♀; Hacet Village (709 m): 27.08.2025, 1♂ 1♀; Erdoğan Village Bedir Hill (528 m): 27.08.2025, 1♂; Büyükada Village Sarımusa (608 m): 29.08.2025, 1♂; Keşap Karabedir District (292 m): 28.08.2025, 1♀; Center- Eriklimanı Village (455 m): 28.08.2025, 1♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adıyaman, Afyonkarahisar, Aksaray, Amasya, Ankara, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Batman, Bolu, Burdur, Çankırı, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elâzığ, Erzincan, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Iğdır, Isparta, İzmir, Karaman, Kars, Kırıkkale, Kırşehir, Kocaeli, Konya, Mardin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Samsun, Siirt, Şanlıurfa, Tokat, Uşak, Yalova, Zonguldak (Dursun, 2011; Yazıcı, 2022)

Gerromorpha: Gerroidea: Gerridae: Gerrinae: Gerrini

***Gerris lacustris* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Uçarlı District dere (60 m): 19.08.2025, 2♀♀; Yaslıbahçe Village, stream (303 m): 20.08.2025, 2♂♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Afyonkarahisar, Ağrı, Antalya, Ardahan, Aydın, Burdur, Bolu, Çorum, Denizli, Edirne, Erzincan, Giresun, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, Karabük, Kilis, Muğla, Sakarya, Samsun, Sinop, Sivas, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Trabzon, Van (Dursun & Fent, 2019; Banbal & Fent, 2020).

Gerromorpha: Hydrometroidea: Hydrometridae

***Hydrometra stagnorum* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Uçarlı District dere (60 m): 19.08.2025, 2♂♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Amasya, Aksaray, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Bartın, Bitlis, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Edirne, Erzincan, Gümüşhane, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Kırklareli, Kırşehir, Konya, Mersin, Muğla, Niğde, Samsun, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Tokat, Tunceli (Dursun & Fent, 2019; Banbal & Fent, 2020; Özdamar & Kiyak, 2024). **First record for Giresun Province.**

Pentatomomorpha: Coreoidea: Coreidae: Coreinae

***Coreus marginatus marginatus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yaslıbahçe Village, graveyard (433 m): 19.08.2025, 5♂♂ 2♀♀; Kuzköy (455 m): 19.08.2025, 1♀; Saraçlı District (53 m): 21.08.2025, 5♂♂ 4♀♀; Alibeyköy (378 m): 26.08.2025, 1♀; Erdoğan Village Bedir Hill (528 m): 27.08.2025, 1♀; Center- Eriklimanı Village (455 m): 28.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Ağrı, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Ardahan, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bingöl, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çorum, Denizli, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Hatay, Isparta, Iğdır, İstanbul, İzmir, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kocaeli, Kütahya, Malatya, Mardin, Mersin, Mersin, Muğla, Muş, Osmaniye, Rize, Samsun, Sinop,

Sivas, Tokat, Trabzon, Tunceli, Van (Fent & Dursun, 2019; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023)

***Gonocerus acuteangulatus* (Goeze, 1778)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yalıköy (83 m): 28.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bursa, Bolu, Çanakkale, Çorum, Denizli, Edirne, Erzurum, Giresun, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İzmir, Kayseri, Kırşehir, Manisa, Muğla, Sivas, Tokat (Akman & Dursun, 2021; Dursun & Fent, 2022).

Pentatomomorpha: Coreoidea: Rhopalidae: Rhopalinae: Rhopalini

***Corizus hyoscyami hyoscyami* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Saraçlı District (53 m): 21.08.2025, 1♂; Ericealan Plateau, next to the forest (1920 m): 22.08.2025, 1♂; Yalıköy (83 m): 28.08.2025, 1♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Ağrı, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Ardahan, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Iğdır, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kırklareli, Konya, Kütahya, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Muş, Ordu, Siirt, Sinop, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Uşak, Van, Zonguldak (Akman & Dursun, 2021; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023)

***Liorhysus hyalinus* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Talipli Village (218 m): 19.08.2025, 2♂♂ 2♀♀; Kuşluhan Village (378 m): 20.08.2025, 1♂; Saraçlı District (53 m): 21.08.2025, 1♂; Erdoğan Village Bedir Hill (528 m): 27.08.2025, 2♀♀; Yalıköy (83 m): 28.08.2025, 2♂♂ 1♀; Büyükkada Village (241 m): 29.08.2025, 1♀; Keşap Karabedir District (292 m): 28.08.2025, 1♂ 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: It is common in all regions, including Giresun(Çerçi et all., 2024).

***Rhopalus subrufus* (Gmelin, 1790)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yasıbahçe Village, graveyard (433 m): 19.08.2025, 1♂; Kuzköy (455 m): 19.08.2025, 1♂ 1♂; Kuşluhan Village (378 m): 20.08.2025, 1♂; Saraçlı District (53 m): 21.08.2025, 1♀; Ericealan Plateau, next to the forest (1920 m): 22.08.2025, 1♂ 1♀; Karapınar Plateau (1893 m): 23.08.2025, 1♂; Ericealan Plateau forest (1910 m): 23.08.2025, 2♀♀; Alibeyköy (378 m): 26.08.2025, 2♂♂ 2♀♀; Hacet Village (709 m): 27.08.2025, 1♂ 1♀; Erdoğan Village Bedir Hill (528 m): 27.08.2025, 1♀; Büyükkada Village (241 m): 29.08.2025, 1♂ 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Artvin, Bolu, Çankırı, Çorum, Düzce, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Hatay, İstanbul, Karabük, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Mardin, Sivas, Sinop, Tokat (Dursun, 2009; Fent & Dursun, 2019; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Yazıcı et al., 2022).

First record for Giresun Province.

***Stictopleurus abutilon* (Rossi, 1790)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yaslıbahçe Village, graveyard (433 m): 19.08.2025, 1♀; Kuşluhan Village (378 m): 20.08.2025, 1♀; Keşap Karabedir District (292 m): 28.08.2025, 2♂♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Amasya, Bolu, Çankırı, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Hatay, Iğdır, Karabük, Kastamonu, Mardin, Tokat (Dursun, 2009; Fent & Dursun, 2019; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Yazıcı et al., 2022). **First record for the Eastern Black Sea Region.**

***Stictopleurus punctatonervosus* (Goeze, 1778)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Burunucu Village Dikmen Hill (475 m): 19.08.2025, 1♂; Kuşluhan Village (378 m): 20.08.2025, 2♂♂ 2♀♀; Yeşilhisar Village (100 m): 21.08.2025, 2♂♂ 2♀♀; Hacet Village (709 m): 27.08.2025, 1♀; Erdoğan Village Bedir Hill (528 m): 27.08.2025, 3♂♂ 1♀; Büyükada Village Sarımusa (608 m): 29.08.2025, 2♂♂ 1♀; Dereli- Taşlıca Village (204 m): 28.08.2025, 2♂♂ 6♀♀; Keşap Karabedir District (292 m): 28.08.2025, 2♂♂ 3♀♀; Center- Eriklimanı Village (455 m): 28.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Antalya, Ardahan, Artvin, Aydın, Bartın, Bayburt, Çankırı, Düzce, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Iğdır, İstanbul, İzmir, Karabük, Kars, Kastamonu, Kocaeli, Manisa, Ordu, Samsun, Sinop, Sivas, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Tunceli, Yozgat (Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Dursun, 2019; Yazıcı et al., 2022)

***Stictopleurus subtomentosus* (Rey, 1888)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Kuşluhan Village (378 m): 20.08.2025, 1♀; Yeşilhisar Village (100 m): 21.08.2025, 1♀; Erdoğan Village Bedir Hill (528 m): 27.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Bilecik, Bitlis, Burdur, Çanakkale, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hakkâri, Hatay, Karaman, Kars, Kayseri, Kütahya, Manisa, Niğde, Osmaniye, Siirt, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Tokat, Uşak, Van (Çerçi & Koçak, 2023). **First record for the Eastern Black Sea Region.**

Pentatomomorpha: Coreoidea: Stenocephalidae***Dicranocephalus albipes* (Fabricius, 1781)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yaslıbahçe Village, graveyard (433 m): 19.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Ağrı, Amasya, Ankara, Artvin, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bolu, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Iğdır, İstanbul, İzmir, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kırklareli, Konya, Kütahya, Mardin, Muğla, Muş, Sakarya, Samsun, Siirt, Sinop, Sivas, Tokat, Uşak, Van (Fent & Dursun, 2019; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023)

Pentatomomorpha: Lygaeoidea: Lygaeidae: Ischnorhynchinae***Kleidocerys resedae resedae* (Panzer, 1797)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yalıköy (83 m): 28.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Balıkesir, Edirne, İstanbul (Çamlıca), Kırklareli, Muğla, Tekirdağ, Erzurum. (Fent & Dursun, 2024). **First record for the Black Sea Region.**

Pentatomomorpha: Lygaeoidea: Lygaeidae: Lygaeinae

***Melanocoryphus tristrami* (Douglas & Scott, 1868)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Kuşluhan Village (378 m): 20.08.2025, 3♂♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bilecik, Bitlis, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Hatay, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Karabük, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Kırklareli, Konya, Kütahya, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Niğde, Sakarya, Samsun, Sinop, Tekirdağ, Uşak, Zonguldak (Fent & Dursun, 2024). **First record for the Eastern Black Sea Region.**

***Spilostethus pandurus* (Scopoli, 1763)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yaslıbahçe Village (490 m): 18.08.2025, 1♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bilecik, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale (Bozcaada, Gökçeada), Çankırı, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elâzığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Giresun, Hakkâri, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kayseri, Kilis, Kırklareli, Kırşehir, Konya, Kütahya, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Muş, Niğde, Osmaniye, Rize, Şanlıurfa, Uşak, Van, Zonguldak (Fent & Dursun, 2024).

Pentatomomorpha: Lygaeoidea: Lygaeidae: Orsillinae: Nysiini

***Nysius cymoides* (Spinola, 1837)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yaslıbahçe Village, graveyard (433 m): 19.08.2025, 1♂; Talipli Village (218 m): 19.08.2025, 1♀; Kuşluhan Village (378 m): 20.08.2025, 1♂; Yeşilhisar Village (100 m): 21.08.2025, 2♂♂; Ericealan Plateau, next to the forest (1920 m): 22.08.2025, 1♀; Ezeltere Village (1581 m): 22.08.2025, 1♀; Erdoğan Village Bedir Hill (528 m): 27.08.2025, 1♂ 5♀♀; Büyükada Village (241 m): 29.08.2025, 1♂ 1♀; Keşap Karabedir District (292 m): 28.08.2025, 5♀♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Adıyaman, Aksaray, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Batman, Bayburt, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elâzığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kars, Kayseri, Kilis, Kırklareli, Kırşehir, Kocaeli, Konya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Muş, Nevşehir, Niğde, Osmaniye, Siirt, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Şırnak, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Van, Yalova, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Fent & Dursun, 2024). **First record for Giresun Province.**

***Nysius ericae ericae* (Schilling, 1829)**

Material examined: Giresun: Center- Kayadibi District (376 m): 28.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Bolu, Edirne, Gaziantep, Hatay, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kayseri, Kilis, Kırklareli, Manisa, Mersin, Nevşehir, Niğde, Osmaniye, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Fent & Dursun, 2024). **First record for the Eastern Black Sea Region.**

***Nysius graminicola graminicola* (Kolenati, 1845)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Kuşluhan Village (378 m): 20.08.2025, 1♂; Saraçlı District (53 m): 21.08.2025, 4♂♂ 2♀♀; Yeşilhisar Village (100 m): 21.08.2025, 2♂♂ 4♀♀; Dereli- Taşlıca Village (204 m): 28.08.2025, 2♂♂ 1♀; Center- Kayadibi District (376 m): 28.08.2025, 1♂ 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Edirne, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hatay, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kilis, Kocaeli, Konya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Sinop, Şanlıurfa, Tekirdağ, Uşak, Zonguldak (Fent & Dursun, 2024). **First record for Giresun Province.**

***Nysius senecionis senecionis* (Schilling, 1829)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Kuşluhan Village (378 m): 20.08.2025, 1♀; Saraçlı District (53 m): 21.08.2025, 2♂♂ 2♀♀; Yeşilhisar Village (100 m): 21.08.2025, 1♀; Erdoğan Village Bedir Hill (528 m): 27.08.2025, 1♂; Dereli- Taşlıca Village (204 m): 28.08.2025, 1♂; Center- Kayadibi District (376 m): 28.08.2025, 1♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Bayburt, Bolu, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Hatay, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kayseri, Kilis, Kırklareli, Kocaeli, Konya, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Niğde, Sakarya, Tekirdağ, Zonguldak (Fent & Dursun, 2024). **First record for Giresun Province.**

Pentatomomorpha: Lygaeoidea: Rhyparochromidae: Rhyparochrominae: Drymini

***Scolopostethus pictus* (Schilling, 1829)**

Material examined: Giresun: Center- Kayadibi District (376 m): 28.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Antalya, Balıkesir, Bursa, Düzce, Edirne, Hatay, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kocaeli, Mersin, Muş, Ordu, Osmaniye (Fent & Aktaş, 2008; Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2024). **First record for Giresun Province.**

Pentatomomorpha: Lygaeoidea: Rhyparochromidae: Rhyparochrominae: Megalonotini

***Megalonotus chiragra* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Karapınar Plateau (1893 m): 23.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Afyonkarahisar, Ankara, Edirne, İzmir, Manisa, Niğde (Önder *et al.*, 2006; Kıyak & Akar, 2010; Yence & Fent, 2023) **First record for the Black Sea Region.**

***Megalonotus sabulicola* (Thomson, 1870)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yaslıbahçe Village (490 m): 18.08.2025, 1♂; Büyükkada Village Sarımusa (608 m): 29.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Bursa, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Erzurum, İzmir, Hatay, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Kastamonu, Kırklareli, Kütahya, Manisa, Mersin, Niğde (Önder *et al.*, 2006; Yazıcı *et al.*, 2015; Fent & Dursun, 2016; Fent *et al.*, 2022; Yence & Fent, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2024). **First record for the Eastern Black Sea Region.**

Pentatomomorpha: Lygaeoidea: Rhyparochromidae: Rhyparochrominae: Myodochini
***Paraparomius leptopoides* (Baerensprung, 1859)**

Material examined: Giresun: Center- Kayadibi District (376 m): 28.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Hatay, İstanbul, Karaman (Çerçi & Koçak, 2023). **First record for the Black Sea Region.**

Pentatomomorpha: Lygaeoidea: Rhyparochromidae: Rhyparochrominae: Rhyparochromini
***Beosus maritimus* (Scopoli, 1763)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Kuşluhan Village (378 m): 20.08.2025, 2♂♂; Yeşilhisar Village (100 m): 21.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Adıyaman, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Giresun, Hatay, Isparta, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Manisa, Mersin, Niğde, Osmaniye, Van, Zonguldak (Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Yence & Fent, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2024).

***Beosus quadripunctatus* (Müller, 1766)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yaslıbahçe Village, graveyard (433 m): 19.08.2025, 1♂; Erdoğan Village, Bedir Hill (528 m): 27.08.2025, 1♀; Hacet Village (709 m): 27.08.2025, 1♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Ağrı, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bilecik, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzurum, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Hatay, Iğdır, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırklareli, Konya, Kütahya, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Muğla, Niğde, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Siirt, Sinop, Tekirdağ, Uşak, Yalova, Zonguldak (Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Yence & Fent, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2024). **First record for Giresun Province.**

***Peritrechus gracilicornis* Puton, 1877**

Material examined: Giresun: Center- Kayadibi District (376 m): 28.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Balıkesir, Bingöl, Bitlis, Bursa, Çankırı, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Erzurum, Hakkari, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Mersin, Niğde, Ordu, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Sinop, Yalova, Zonguldak (Lodos *et al.*, 1999; Péricart, 1998c; Önder *et al.*,

2006; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Küçükbasmacı & Kiyak, 2015; Yazıcı et al., 2015; Fent & Dursun, 2016). **First record for Giresun Province.**

***Rhyparochromus vulgaris* (Schilling, 1829)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yaslıbahçe Village (490 m): 18.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Amasya, Ankara, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Denizli, Düzce, Edirne, Erzincan, Erzurum, Hatay, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Karaman, Kütahya, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Osmaniye, Tunceli, Uşak, Van (Çerçi & Koçak, 2023; Eser & Dursun, 2024). **First record for the Eastern Black Sea Region.**

Pentatomomorpha: Pentatomoidea: Pentatomidae: Pentatominae: Aeliini

***Aelia acuminata* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Burunucu Village Dikmen Hill (475 m): 19.08.2025, 3♂♂ 3♀♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Adıyaman, Afyonkarahisar, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Edirne, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Hatay, Iğdır, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kırklareli, Kırşehir, Kocaeli, Konya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Niğde, Osmaniye, Rize, Sakarya, Samsun, Siirt, Sinop, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Şırnak, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Trabzon, Tunceli, Uşak, Zonguldak (Dursun & Kartal, 2008; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

***Neottiglossa leporina* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1830)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Burunucu Village Dikmen Hill (475 m): 19.08.2025, 1♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Amasya, Ankara, Bartın, Bolu, Bursa, Çankırı, Diyarbakır, Elâzığ, Erzurum, Iğdır, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Kars, Kastamonu, Kırklareli, Muğla, Ordu, Samsun, Sinop, Tokat, Zonguldak (Dursun & Kartal, 2008; Fent & Dursun, 2022). **First record for Giresun Province.**

Pentatomomorpha: Pentatomoidea: Pentatomidae: Pentatominae: Cappaeini

***Halyomorpha halys* (Stål, 1855)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yaslıbahçe Village (490 m): 18.08.2025, 2♀♀; Yalıköy (83 m): 28.08.2025, 1♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Ankara, Artvin, Aydın, Bartın, Bursa, Eskişehir, Giresun, İstanbul, İzmir, Ordu, Rize, Samsun, Trabzon, Yalova (Fent & Dursun, 2022).

Pentatomomorpha: Pentatomoidea: Pentatomidae: Pentatominae: Carpocorini

***Carpocoris mediterraneus mediterraneus* Tamanini, 1958**

Material examined: Giresun: Dereli- Taşlıca Village (204 m): 28.08.2025, 3♂♂ 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Edirne, Elâzığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Konya, Kütahya, Kırklareli, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Muş, Ordu, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Samsun, Sinop, Sivas, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Trabzon, Yalova, Zonguldak (Fent & Dursun, 2022).

***Carpocoris purpureipennis* (De Geer, 1773)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yaslıbahçe Village, graveyard (433 m): 19.08.2025, 2♂♂; Burunucu Village Dikmen Hill (475 m): 19.08.2025, 1♀; Kuşluhan Village (378 m): 20.08.2025, 2♀♀; Hacet Village (709 m): 27.08.2025, 1♀; Erdoğan Village, Bedir Hill (528 m): 27.08.2025, 2♂♂; Yalıköy (83 m): 28.08.2025, 1♂ 1♀; Dereli- Taşlıca Village (204 m): 28.08.2025 2♂♂ 2♀♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bitlis, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Konya, Kütahya, Kırklareli, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Niğde, Ordu, Osmaniye, Samsun, Sinop, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Trabzon, Tunceli, Yalova, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Fent & Dursun, 2022).

***Dolycoris baccarum* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Saraçlı District (53 m): 21.08.2025, 1♂; Hacet Village (709 m): 27.08.2025, 1♀; Büyükada Village Sarımusa (608 m): 29.08.2025, 1♂; Dereli- Taşlıca Village (204 m): 28.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Adıyaman, Afyonkarahisar, Ağrı, Aksaray, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Ardahan, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Batman, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Hakkari, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kilis, Kırıkkale, Kırklareli, Kocaeli, Konya, Kütahya, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Muş, Nevşehir, Niğde, Ordu, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Samsun, Siirt, Sinop, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Şırnak, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Trabzon, Tunceli, Uşak, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Fent & Dursun, 2022).

Pentatomomorpha: Pentatomoidea: Pentatomidae: Pentatominae: Eysarcorini

***Eysarcoris aeneus* (Scopoli, 1763)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yaslıbahçe Village (490 m): 18.08.2025, 1♀; Yaslıbahçe Village, graveyard (433 m): 19.08.2025, 1♂ 2♀♀; Talipli Village (218 m): 19.08.2025, 1♀; Tepecik Village (624 m): 20.08.2025, 1♀; Saraçlı District (53 m): 21.08.2025, 1♂; Alibeyköy (378 m): 26.08.2025, 1♂; Keşap Karabedir District (292 m): 28.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Bartın, Bayburt, Edirne, Kırklareli, Ordu, Samsun, Tekirdağ (Fent & Dursun, 2022). **First record for Giresun Province.**

***Eysarcoris ventralis* (Westwood, 1837)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Talipli Village (218 m): 19.08.2025, 1♂ 2♀♀; Saraçlı District (53 m): 21.08.2025, 1♀; Yeşilhisar Village (100 m): 21.08.2025, 1♂; Hacet Village (709 m): 27.08.2025, 1♂ 2♀♀; Erdoğan Village Bedir Hill (528 m): 27.08.2025, 2♀♀; Yalıköy (83 m): 28.08.2025, 1♂; Büyükkada Village (241 m): 29.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Adıyaman, Ağrı, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Edirne, Elâzığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kocaeli, Konya, Kırklareli, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Muş, Nevşehir, Niğde, Ordu, Osmaniye, Rize, Sakarya, Samsun, Siirt, Sinop, Sivas, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Trabzon, Uşak, Zonguldak. (Fent & Dursun, 2022). **First record for Giresun Province.**

Pentatomomorpha: Pentatomoidea: Pentatomidae: Pentatominae: Nezarini***Nezara viridula* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yaslıbahçe Village (490 m): 18.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Adıyaman, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Düzce, Edirne, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Giresun, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kars, Kastamonu, Kocaeli, Kırklareli, Malatya, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Ordu, Osmaniye, Rize, Sakarya, Samsun, Sinop, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Trabzon, Tunceli, Zonguldak (Fent & Dursun, 2022).

***Palomena prasina* (Linnaeus, 1761)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yaslıbahçe Village (490 m): 18.08.2025, 5♂♂ 2♀♀; Alibeyköy (378 m): 26.08.2025, 1♂ 1♀; Hacet Village (709 m): 27.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bilecik, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Düzce, Edirne, Elâzığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Hakkâri, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kocaeli, Konya, Kütahya, Kırklareli, Manisa, Mersin, Ordu, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Samsun, Sinop, Sivas, Şırnak, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Trabzon, Tunceli, Zonguldak (Fent & Dursun, 2022).

Pentatomomorpha: Pentatomoidea: Pentatomidae: Pentatominae: Strachiini***Eurydema (Eurydema) oleracea* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yeşilhisar Village (100 m): 21.08.2025, 1♂; Yalıköy (83 m): 28.08.2025, 2♀♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Afyonkarahisar, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Ardahan, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bolu, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Edirne, Eskişehir, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kars, Kastamonu, Kırklareli, Kocaeli, Konya, Kütahya, Manisa, Mersin, Niğde, Ordu, Osmaniye, Rize, Sakarya, Samsun, Sinop, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Trabzon, Tunceli, Uşak, Yalova, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Fent & Dursun, 2022).

Pentatomomorpha: Pentatomoidea: Pentatomidae: Podopinae: Graphosomatini
***Graphosoma italicum italicum* (O.F. Müller, 1766)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Yalıköy (83 m): 28.08.2025, 2♂♂ 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Adıyaman, Ağrı, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bolu, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Düzce, Edirne, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Konya, Kütahya, Kırklareli, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Sinop, Sivas, Tekirdağ, Tunceli, Yalova, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Fent & Dursun, 2022). **First record for Giresun Province.**

Pentatomomorpha: Pentatomoidea: Plataspidae: Coptosomatinae
***Coptosoma mucronatum* Seidenstücker, 1963**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Erdoğan Village Bedir Hill (528 m): 27.08.2025, 1♂ 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Ankara, Burdur, Edirne, Isparta, Kahramanmaraş, Kırklareli, Konya, Kütahya, Mersin, Niğde, Tekirdağ (Seidenstücker, 1963; Lodos & Önder, 1978; Lodos et al., 1998; Doğanlar et al., 2007; Fent & Aktaç, 2007). **First record for the Black Sea Region.**

Pentatomomorpha: Pentatomoidea: Scutelleridae: Eurygasterinae
***Eurygaster testudinaria* (Geoffroy, 1785)**

Material examined: Giresun: Dereli- Taşlıca Village (204 m): 28.08.2025, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Amasya, Ankara, Ardahan, Artvin, Bartın, Çankırı, Edirne, Erzurum, İstanbul, Kahramanmaraş, Kastamonu, Kırklareli, Samsun, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Zonguldak (Fent & Aktaç, 2009; Yazıcı et al., 2022). **First record for Giresun Province.**

Pentatomomorpha: Pyrrhocoroidea: Pyrrhocoridae
***Pyrrhocoris apterus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Giresun: Bulancak- Büyükada Village (241 m): 29.08.2025, 16 nimf.

Distribution in Türkiye: Adana, Adıyaman, Ağrı, Ankara, Antalya, Ardahan, Artvin, Aydın, Bayburt, Bilecik, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Denizli, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Giresun, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Konya, Malatya, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Niğde, Sakarya, Siirt, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Tokat, Trabzon (Yazıcı et al., 2022)

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this study, conducted in 26 localities in Bulancak District of Giresun in August 2025, 45 genera and 63 species/subspecies belonging to 15 families of Heteroptera

were identified. Their distribution according to families is as follows: Anthocoridae 2 genera and 3 species, Miridae 7 genera and 13 species, Tingidae 2 genera and 2 species, Nabidae 2 genera and 4 species, Coreidae 2 genera and 2 species, Rhopalidae 4 genera and 6 species, Lygaeidae 4 genera and 7 species, Ryparochromidae 6 genera and 8 species, Pentatomidae 10 genera and 12 species, and 1 genus and 1 species from the families Gerridae, Hydrometridae, Plataspidae, Scutelleridae and Pyrrhocoridae.

When the new records identified in the study are evaluated, 7 species (*Orius vicinus*, *Dicyphus albonasutus*, *Orthops montanus*, *Kleidocerys resedae resedae*, *Coptosoma mucronatum*, *Megalonotus chiragra* and *Paraparomius leptopoides*) are new records for the entire Black Sea Region.

Of these species, *P. leptopoides* is particularly rare in Türkiye. The other species are known from only a few localities. Eight species (*Stenotus binotatus*, *Melanocoryphus tristrami*, *Nysius ericae ericae*, *Stictopleurus abutilon* and *Stictopleurus subtomentosus*, *Megalonotus sabulicola*, *Rhyparochromus vulgaris* and *Himacerus apterus*) were considered new records for the Eastern Black Sea Region. 24 species were identified for the first time in Giresun Province (Table 2).

Stenodema holsata, *Stephanitis caucasica*, and *Paraparomius leptopoides* are rare species in Türkiye, with their distribution limited to a few provinces. *S. holsata* is known from Trabzon and Artvin, located in the same region as Giresun, as well as from Kars in the nearby region and Kocaeli in Western Anatolia.

S. caucasica has been recorded from three provinces so far: Artvin, another province in the Eastern Black Sea Region; Sivas, which is Giresun's southwest neighbor; and Iğdır, which borders Armenia.

This species is also quite rare in its Palearctic distribution and has so far been recorded outside of Türkiye, in Armenia, Georgia, and the Caucasus part of Russia (Aukema, 2018).

This study has been useful in adding new locality information to the species' distribution. *P. leptopoides* is known from Istanbul, in addition to Hatay and Karaman in the south of the country.

The detection of the species in Giresun strengthens the belief that it has a wider distribution area.

Table 2. Species identified in the study (*: New record for Giresun province; **: New record for the Eastern Black Sea Region; ***: New record for the entire Black Sea Region).

Family	Species
ANTHOCORIDAE	<i>Anthocoris nemorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)*
	<i>Orius minutus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Orius vicinus</i> (Ribaut, 1923)***
MIRIDAE	<i>Dicyphus albonasutus</i> Wagner, 1951***
	<i>Adelphocoris lineolatus</i> (Goeze, 1778)*
	<i>Adelphocoris seticornis</i> (Fabricius, 1775)*
	<i>Liocoris tripustulatus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)*
	<i>Lygus rugulipennis</i> Poppius, 1911
	<i>Lygus pratensis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)*
	<i>Orthops basalis</i> (A. Costa, 1853)*
	<i>Orthops kalmii</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)*
	<i>Orthops montanus</i> (Schilling, 1837)***
	<i>Stenotus binotatus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)**
	<i>Stenodema calcarata</i> (Fallén, 1807)*
	<i>Stenodema holsata</i> (Fabricius, 1787)*
<i>Stenodema laevigata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	
TINGIDAE	<i>Corythucha arcuata</i> (Say, 1832)*
	<i>Stephanitis caucasica</i> Kiritshenko, 1951*
NABIDAE	<i>Himacerus apterus</i> (Fabricius, 1798)**
	<i>Himacerus mirmicoides</i> (O. Costa, 1834)
	<i>Nabis punctatus punctatus</i> A. Costa, 1847
	<i>Nabis rugosus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
GERRIDAE	<i>Gerris lacustris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
HYDROMETRIDAE	<i>Hydrometra stagnorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)*
COREIDAE	<i>Coreus marginatus marginatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Gonocerus acuteangulatus</i> (Goeze, 1778)
RHOPALIDAE	<i>Corizus hyoscyami hyoscyami</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Liorhyssus hyalinus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)
	<i>Rhopalus subrufus</i> (Gmelin, 1790)*
	<i>Stictopleurus abutilon</i> (Rossi, 1790)**
	<i>Stictopleurus punctatonervosus</i> (Goeze, 1778)
	<i>Stictopleurus subtomentosus</i> (Rey, 1888)**

Table 2 (contunied). Species identified in the study (*: New record for Giresun province; **: New record for the Eastern Black Sea Region; ***: New record for the entire Black Sea Region).

STENOCEPHALIDAE	<i>Dicranocephalus albipes</i> (Fabricius, 1781)
LYGAEIDAE	<i>Kleidocerys resedae resedae</i> (Panzer, 1797)***
	<i>Melanocoryphus tristrami</i> (Douglas & Scott, 1868)**
	<i>Spilostethus pandurus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)
	<i>Nysius cymoides</i> (Spinola, 1837)*
	<i>Nysius ericae ericae</i> (Schilling, 1829)**
	<i>Nysius graminicola graminicola</i> (Kolenati, 1845)*
	<i>Nysius senecionis senecionis</i> (Schilling, 1829)*
RHYPAROCHROMIDAE	<i>Scolopostethus pictus</i> (Schilling, 1829)*
	<i>Megalonotus chiragra</i> (Fabricius, 1794)***
	<i>Megalonotus sabulicola</i> (Thomson, 1870)**
	<i>Paraparomius leptopoides</i> (Baerensprung, 1859)***
	<i>Beosus maritimus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)
	<i>Beosus quadripunctatus</i> (Müller, 1766)*
	<i>Peritrechus gracilicornis</i> Puton, 1877*
<i>Rhyparochromus vulgaris</i> (Schilling, 1829)**	
PENTATOMIDAE	<i>Aelia acuminata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Neottiglossa leporina</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1830)*
	<i>Halyomorpha halys</i> (Stål, 1855)
	<i>Carpocoris mediterraneus mediterraneus</i> Tamanini, 1958
	<i>Carpocoris purpureipennis</i> (De Geer, 1773)
	<i>Dolycoris baccarum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Eysarcoris aeneus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)*
	<i>Eysarcoris ventralis</i> (Westwood, 1837)*
	<i>Nezara viridula</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Palomena prasina</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)
	<i>Eurydema (Eurydema) oleracea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
<i>Graphosoma italicum italicum</i> (O.F. Müller, 1766)*	
PLATASPIDAE	<i>Coptosoma mucronatum</i> Seidenstücker, 1963***
SCUTELLERIDAE	<i>Eurygaster testudinaria</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)*
PYRRHOCORIDAE	<i>Pyrrhocoris apterus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)

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